

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INVESTMENT

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ABSTRACT

Investments are long-term investments and various industrial, social and economic programs, innovations, business projects and private foreign projects with the goal of economic development. Soglasno teorii mennoy stoimosti deneg, investitsii - eto volozhenie sredstv s tselyu pocheniya vygody v dushchem. Investitsii oznachayut vlozhenie ili rezervirovanie kapitala na opredelennyi vremeni. Osnovnaya tsel etogo — sokhranit stoimost kapitala ili, esli net, uvelichit stoimost kapitala s techeniem vremeni.

The term investment is derived from the Latin word "invest" which means to mobilize funds. This word has entered mostly through Russian literature and it means "oblachat". This word translates into Uzbek and means to dress up.

When defining the concept of investment, this concept is not compatible with the word investment in terms of meaning. Or, the concept of "Investment" has a number of meanings, and it means the investment of money in short, for the purpose of profit, the purchase of shares, bonds, the purchase and production of real assets necessary for the production of goods, as well as intellectual and other (land, natural wealth, etc.) is understood as spending on material wealth and any goods - property and territory together from an economic point of view, i.e. investments are any means that preserve the value of money or increase its value and ensure positive income and positive changes. So, the word investment has a wider meaning, and in addition, it also means to acquire (manage). In a market economy, the problem of investment is treated as similar to the problem of private capital accumulation. At the beginning of the previous analysis of the laws of accumulation, classical political economists (A.Smith, D.Ricardo) were involved, which analyzed their preference on the basis of the process of reproduction of individual capital. In this analysis, the mechanism of capitalization and formation of net profit in the interaction of supply and demand plays the main decisive role. This approach was continued and adopted by the theorists of illiberalism. The work on the future development of macroeconomic analysis of problems in accumulation is related to the work of Dj Keynes, written in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century. It revealed the main economic indicators related to it - the total amount of assets and liabilities, the percentage of capital, working capital and net profit, money supply, the share of national

income in consumption and investment and its size. Dj using the dynamics of macroeconomic parameters. Keynes explained the level of capital utilization and its influence on the process of investment, as well as the mechanism of its formation. The concept of savings category and its connection with the concept of a multiplier and the Keynesian economic method of the economy, which fulfills the function of an additional product and the norm of savings in expanded reproduction, which performs the function of an accelerator, are considered. The Keynesian macroeconomic method became widespread mainly after the war period. In this form and in this form, all sciences oriented to the world economy are accepted as practice, even if it takes into account neoliberalism. The difference between the Keynesian approach and the alternative options is that it reveals the place and role of the state in the mechanism of self-management in the economy, which, according to supporters of liberalism, is the measure of the state in managing the market and defines it.

When explaining the concept of investment, it is impossible to give full meaning to the concept without paying attention to the value of the enterprise. The managers who increase the value of the enterprise are considered as such, and the future strategy of the permanent enterprise is developed and managed by this employee. Determining the system that embodies the value of the enterprise, it consists of 2 parts: - the market value of the personal capital of the enterprise - the market value of the liabilities of the enterprise. The value of the enterprise is mainly explained not by its high capital, but by the condition of the enterprise's capital in providing the services and goods market. This condition determines the direction of the enterprise's investment: if its capital provides growth in profitability and increases the enterprise's competitiveness, then the enterprise's value (tsennost) i increases and its owners become richer. At the same time, the economic theory of enterprise value: the value of an enterprise at any given time is considered by measuring the value of all its future revenues equal to its present value. Most of the authors understand that investments are money spent on reproducing, maintaining and expanding capital. Uzbek scientists also support this concept. D. According to Gozibekov, "Investments generally occur during the conversion of capital for the purposes of preserving the current value of capital and (or) increasing savings of this value. Therefore, they are not consumed during this period and are attached to specific objects and processes for a certain period of time, where they are occupied, where they are exposed to specific and non-specific risks.

In some economic literature published in Russian, it is understood that investment is the expenditure of money, the income of which is used not for consumption, but for the reproduction of total social or individual capital, which consists in finding a higher income or social effect in the future. In some literature, the total types of investments of financial, property and intellectual benefits in various sectors, investment projects for the purpose of development of production, entrepreneurship, profit or other final results are called investments. According to these authors, investments are resources spent on expanding or renewing production, that is, increasing real capital.

But it should also be said that investments are not only resources spent on increasing real capital, these resources are also spent on tangible and intangible assets, and the purchase of securities. Investments are also understood as long-term use of economic resources in

order to generate profit in the future. That is, allocating financial resources for the purpose of capitalization of capital and creation of savings is called investment.

Uzbek scientists: "Investment is the use of financial, material and intellectual assets of individuals and legal entities operating on the basis of entrepreneurship, regardless of the form of ownership, or of the state, in order to achieve economic and social benefits, on any business object within the scope of the Law." In our opinion, the definitions given by the above authors to the concept of "Investment" correspond to the current conditions and requirements of the market economy.

All definitions reveal the economic content of the investment. Candidate of Economics F. Goziev's definition includes all types of investment. However, according to his definition, investment only includes all types of property, financial and intellectual assets in the objects of business activity.

In our opinion, the concepts of investment presented above are only one-sided, they represent either funds invested in the production sector or material, financial and intellectual resources spent on business objects. In our opinion, investment should be understood as a multi-faceted activity, and it means spending free financial resources on objects that will create material and financial wealth in the future, managing property and territories.

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